

A Regionalized Emission Model to Understand PFAS Emission Pathways in the Upper Danube Catchment

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Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) are a group of synthetic chemicals widely used in various household, commercial and industrial products due to their unique properties of oil, water and stain repellency [1]. As research increasingly underscores the persistence and potential toxicity associated with these emerging contaminants, significant concerns for environmental and human health have been raised [2].

The European Green Deal commits to achieving a zero pollution ambition for a toxic-free environment, where the urgent need to address risks from persistent and mobile hazardous chemicals are specifically mentioned [3]. Emission models can serve as tools to quantify these hazardous substances, facilitating the implementation of the EU regulatory instrument for river basin management. This is particularly beneficial for PFASs, as available monitoring data remains limited for substances beyond PFOA and PFOS, and the mechanisms of emission and transport for different PFAS substances via environmental pathways are not fully understood.

Within the framework of the EU project PROMISCES case study 2 [4], we conducted a monitoring campaign lasting 1.5 years, covering six compartments in the upper Danube catchment, extending down to city of Budapest [5]. With the help of monitoring data to understand pollution sources for 18 PFAS substances, and selected river gauges providing possibility for model validation, we further developed an adapted version of the regionalized emission model MoRE. This model enables us to estimate the spatial and temporal variability of several PFASs inputs to the river network in forms of loads and concentrations, from both point sources and various diffuse pathways. The model results provide valuable insights to support water management efforts, particularly in targeted PFAS pollution monitoring and mitigation strategies.

Methodology

The MoRE model system was originally developed as a pathway-oriented tool to model substances inputs to the surface waters [6]. Its flexible structure facilitates the integration of new substances and emission pathways by providing necessary data.

In the PROMISCES project, we adapted the model to include PFASs and identified potential critical pathways for PFAS emission, based on earlier research [7]. These pathways were subsequently implemented to the model, and categorized according to the EU Guidance Document No.28 [8], listed as:

- P1: Atmospheric deposition directly to surface water
- P2: Erosion
- P3: Surface Runoff from unsealed areas
- P4: Groundwater
- P7: Sewer Systems
- P8: Urban wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)
- P9: Individual – treated and untreated – household discharge
- P10: Direct industrial discharge

Where P4, P7 and P10 were further divided into sub-pathways to target the sources more clearly.

The model operates with an annual temporal resolution, covering the period from 2015 to 2021 with possibility to extend. Spatial resolution encompasses 526 sub-catchments with a size of 354 ± 352 km².

Hydrological input parameters for the model were derived from the Wflow model developed by Deltares [9], with enhanced resolution achieved by combining precipitation data from the scaled SPARTACUS dataset [10] and the ERA5 data [11]. Other basic input data were sourced from various open databases or directly requested from local authorities. Substances input data were collected from the project monitoring activities [5] and the DHm3c data inventory [12].

To quantify the uncertainties behind the model inputs variables, the 25th, 50th and 75th percentiles of environmental concentrations for each PFASs were calculated using the regression on order statistics (ROS) method [13], to represent best, base and worst-

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case scenarios. The model results were further validated through in-streams loads and concentrations. In this study, we will present the values of KGE (Kling-Gupta Efficiency) [14].

Result and Discussion

Ten PFAS compounds were selected for validation at 11 monitoring sites, as these substances typically recorded concentrations in the rivers above the limit of quantifications (LOQ). This allows for meaningful comparisons between observed and modelled data. Additionally, the transformations of typical precursors were considered, including the conversion of N-EtFOSAA to PFOS [15], and 6:2 FTS to PFPeA and PFHxA [16].

The results indicate good model performance, with 9 out of 10 selected PFAS achieving a KGE value above 0.5 for loads, and 7 out of 10 for concentrations. Notably, all 5 carboxylic acids (PFCAs) demonstrated very good performance ($KGE > 0.75$) for both loads and concentrations. The model generally performed better for PFCAs and ADONA compared to sulfonic-acids (PFSAs) and GenX, furthermore, with better results in larger catchments. However, results showed constant underestimation for PFHxA, PFOA and PFBS, suggesting the presence of emission sources not accounted for in the modelled pathways.

Pathway contribution analysis reveals significant diffuse input from urban inhabitants via groundwater. This pathway is particularly pronounced at catchment where large cities located, such as Isar (Munich), and the Danube (Vienna, Budapest). Another notable diffuse pathway is the legacy pollution from Gendorf, a long-standing contaminated site [17] that continued to emit PFOA via groundwater.

Additionally, the model shows that surface runoff and background emission via groundwater can be important pathways for certain PFAS compounds. In relatively arid regions within the study area, including Moravia (Czech Republic), western Slovakia and Hungary, direct atmospheric deposition and erosion gain prominence. Furthermore, at sites Svatka, Morava and Ipoly, where the WWTP connection rates are lower, the contributions from individual household discharge pathway can be observed.

Regarding point sources, both industrial direct discharger and WWTPs are shown to be significant contributors to PFAS emissions. The WWTP pathway is evident across all PFAS compounds, whereas industrial direct dischargers are more specifically linked to the emissions of PFCAs, ADONA and GenX. The chemical-park at Gendorf, where the 3M

PFAS production site is located, stands out as a major pollution source, contributing substantially to the emission of short-chain PFCAs, ADONA and GenX. For ADONA, this pathway is responsible for nearly all emission within the study area.

Figure 1 shows the risk of summed PFAS levels exceeding the proposed Environmental Quality Standard (EQS 2022) of 4.4 ng PFOA-equivalent/L and the Drinking Water Directive (DWD 2020) standard of 100 ng/L [18,19]. The impact from the Gendorf site in the Alz catchment is clearly visible, highlighting very high risk regardless of the variants and standards applied. Catchments with large cities or those in arid regions show relatively higher risks in the rivers. If the stricter EQS standard is enforced, more areas will face significant water quality challenges.

Figure 1 Risk maps based on the modelled results

Conclusion

- We developed a regionalized model to quantify PFAS emissions in the upper Danube catchment via pathways. The model demonstrated good performance for the selected PFAS.
- Results indicate that diffuse inputs from urban inhabitants play a significant role in the emissions of most PFASs. The continuous contribution from the legacy contaminated site at Gendorf via groundwater to the PFOA pollution was highlighted.
- The industrial park at Gendorf, along with other industries, were identified as important point sources of PFAS emissions.
- Information from the risk maps and the model can enhance our understanding and enable better management and control of PFAS pollution.

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